

An intelligent deep learning-based approach for electrical energy consumption forecasting in buildings using smart meter data

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Abstract—Forecasting electricity demand is a great way to plan ahead for improving the power generator sector and getting ready for regular operations. The rapid growth of cities has led to a sharp increase in energy demand, resulting in a significant discrepancy between the quantity of energy produced and consumer demand. In order to close the gap between supply and demand, a new prediction model is needed that uses automated methods to dynamically forecast the building's energy consumption. In the proposed method, an intelligent deep learning technique LSTM (Long short-term memory) is accompanied by pre-processing for the forecasting power consumption in a building. The proposed model is evaluated over benchmark datasets that demonstrate a significant reduction in the error rate compared to other methods. The proposed LSTM method achieves better prediction results, thus demonstrating its effectiveness with other methods. Root mean square error (RMSE), mean square error (MSE), and mean absolute error (MAE) are used to evaluate the proposed model. The results indicated that the proposed model error vanishes to reach an RMSE value of 1%, MSE value of 0.3%, and MAE value of 1%. RNN (Recurrent Neural Network), GRU (Gated Recurrent Unit), and Bi-LSTM (Bi-directional Long Short-Term Memory) are taken into consideration for the comparative study, and the research is done to predict energy consumption one month in advance, with 80% of the data being used as the training set and the remaining 20% being used for testing.

Keywords— deep learning; energy consumption; forecasting; error metrics; time series data

1. INTRODUCTION

Over the past 2 decades, energy consumption has increased significantly world-wide as a result of economic growth and an increasing number of people. When it comes to a region's social development, energy is by far the most significant factor, which has a huge impact on its progress and economic growth. The CEA (the Central Electricity Authority) surveys the country every five years to estimate the demand for medium- and long-term periods. The survey included a demand estimate for 2021–22 to 2031–32 under an optimistic scenario based on the attainment of goals established by the government under projects like the National Hydrogen Mission intended to im-pact the electricity demand. Tamil Nadu's power requirement is expected to reach 1,86,106 million units in 2031-32, up from 1,09,914 million units in 2021-22, according to the 20th Electric Power Survey of India report from CEA, which functions under the Union Ministry of Power.

TABLE I
 POWER USAGE IN TAMIL NADU AS COMPILED IN A RECENT SURVEY

Period	2021-22	2031-32
Energy requirements (in million units)	1,09,914	1,86,106
Energy consumption (in million units)	92,625	1,63,156
Peak demand (MW)	16,899	28,291

According to the power usage data shared in Table I, Tamil Nadu’s peak demand is expected to reach 28,291 MW by 2031-32, compared with 16,899 MW in 2021-22. The share of domestic consumption is expected to go up.

Fig. 1 Energy consumption share in Tamil Nadu between 2021-22

Among various categories, residential consumption is expected to increase in the upcoming years [1]. It is interpreted in the form of a pie chart in Fig. 1.

2. RELATED WORKS

The high energy consumption levels of residential buildings necessitate effective management of their energy consumption. As a result, efficient energy planning is essential for energy savings and is made feasible by models that accurately estimate energy consumption. A crucial yet difficult aspect of time series data analysis is fore-casting. The electricity prediction strategies are categorized into four types: very-short, short, medium, and long-term. Time series data is the main factor that affects how well and accurately data analysis and forecasting tools work. But other domain-specific factors affect predictions, like seasonality, economic ups and downs, and unexpected events, as well as changes within the company that's producing the data [2].

Statistical and artificial intelligence (AI) models have been used in the past to predict energy production from renewable sources and to predict how much electricity will be used. In the beginning, statistical models like auto regressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) [3], linear regression [4], Kalman filtering [10], and clustering [13] were used to predict electricity loads. These models work well for learning linear data, but they're not good enough for learning complex electricity loads. In [16], the author used the Kalman filter

to estimate the household load over different time horizons and sample periods. They claim that the sampling rate chosen is a trade-off between precision and computational complexity. This clustering is useful for the customers to know about their consumption and also it leads to knowing about the peak demand. In their paper [24], they came up with a basic feature-based algorithm to help reduce the extreme dimensionality associated with load time series by transforming them into map models that could be easily clustered.

In addition, AI models are capable of learning non-linear complex and linear electrical loads, which are classified into two categories: shallow and deep learning. Shallow-based methods include Random Forest [14], wavelet neural network [15], support vector machine (SVM) [17], artificial neural network (ANN) [18], and extreme learning machine (ELM) [22]. In [20], a variety of models were employed, including Statistical Modeling (SVM), Classification and Regression trees, and multilayer perceptron neural networks (MLP). The authors concluded that by combining household behavioral data with historical electricity usage data derived from individual households, forecasting accuracy could be significantly improved. The MAPE for the neural networks was 51% and the MAPE for the SVM was 48%. However, the acquired error rate is very large to conclude. When compared to statistical methods, shallow based algorithms perform well, however, they struggle in feature mining. These methods therefore need more features and select robust features to improve the accuracy of the predictions. It is difficult for these approaches to achieve excellent feature extraction. In addition, due to a limited number of parameters, these methods cannot generalize across multiple datasets due to the limited number of hypotheses.

Deep learning techniques can address the issues associated with shallow based methods by utilizing multi-layer processing, as well as hierarchical feature learning from electrical historical data. In recent years, RNNs and CNNs have been proposed as two powerful architectures for analyzing time series data in the literature.

For example, in [23], a study proposed a deep CNN for the prediction of day-ahead loads and compared its performance to that of an ARIMA, ELM, RNN, and CNN. Several other studies also employed RNN models for the prediction of electricity loads. In [25], researchers employed RNN, GRU, and LSTM models to predict electricity loads in Turkey and significantly reduced the error rate. In addition, the researchers in [26] created a model based on LSTM that could be used to predict energy over time and compared it to other models.

Even though there is a great deal of research conducted on household electricity usage, there are certain shortcomings that can be identified. Generally, the majority of studies do not provide a comprehensive analysis of the relationship between residential electricity usage and the interactions between the various factors that influence it, such as time-related factors (season, month, day, hour) [6], air quality-related factors (particulate matter, ground-level ozone) [7], weather-related factors (rainfall, temperature, humidity) [8], and economic factors (GDP (Gross Domestic Product), unemployment, inflation) [9]. Another critique of the existing literature is the general lack of connection between electricity consumption and household data and usage history. Household factors as well as historical energy consumption are expected to have a significant impact on future usage. The majority of research focuses exclusively on analyzing consumption trends based on dwelling and socioeconomic data, disregarding recent historical usage (within the last few months).

The summary of the past work is: (i) Weather plays a significant role in reducing the accuracy of the predictions. Therefore, further research should be conducted to understand the effects of weather on electricity forecasting and to incorporate weather factors into the predictions by measuring the impact and contribution of each variable on the consumption profile. (ii) Prediction accuracy fell short of expectations, i.e., the error rate did not fall within a reasonable range. So, there is a need for an efficient deep learning model to mitigate the error (iii) Short-term forecasting gives better accuracy than medium and long-term forecasting. Therefore, here the short-term prediction (iv) Single deep learning method is not used in many of the studies. This research work is considered a single deep learning network. This research work attempts to fill these identified gaps and incorporate all these challenges to get better accuracy results. The remainder

of this paper is structured as follows: In the next section, the different deep learning prediction models were discussed based on this study and the methodology for analyzing residential building electricity consumption patterns will be described. Furthermore, the main results and findings are interpreted. Finally, the paper concludes with a critical discussion of the implications of our findings and proposes avenues for future research.

3. DEEP LEARNING PREDICTION MODEL

In this literature, different deep learning models were tested and among those, the best model was chosen and evaluated their prediction performance. Among deep learning models, RNNs can support dependencies between successive time steps, so they can store past data in time series and are commonly used to forecast sequential operations. However, RNNs face the issue of vanishing/exploding gradient [30]. Thus, different models were proposed in the literature such as LSTM [31] and GRU neural networks [32] to overcome the RNN vanishing gradient problem and exploding gradients. Vanishing gradients are gradients that disappear and wash out as soon as they reach the end or beginning of the gradient. Vanishing gradients occur when the input or gradient information passes through many layers. This causes RNNs to have a hard time capturing long-term dependencies. As a result, RNN training will be very difficult. Exploding gradients refer to instances where information about an input or gradient is passed through multiple layers, resulting in a large gradient at the end or the beginning layer. This makes it difficult to train RNNs. Gradient is a partial derivative of a function's output of its inputs. It measures how much a function's output changes to the changes in its inputs.

LSTM networks are a specialized subset of RNN networks, which are commonly employed to solve both linear and non-linear time series issues. LSTMs are neural networks that are designed to address the issue of vanishing and exploding gradients, which can impede the formation of long-lasting dependencies. To address this issue, three gates are used in LSTM networks to store and access long-term relevant information, while simultaneously discarding irrelevant information. These gates are the update gate, which determines the information to be used for the memory state up-date, and the output gate, which is the output value to be inputted the following time. These gates allow for a continuous stream of data to be written, read, and reset during the learning process. By controlling the input gate, the information can be stored and accessed in the long term, thus minimizing the issue of vanishing gradient. Additionally, the forget gate allows for the retention or overpassing of information from the preceding time. Fig.2 presents an illustration of general LSTM architecture.

Fig. 2 The general LSTM architecture

In the architecture as illustrated in Fig. 2, the LSTM cell is composed of a cell state c , a hidden state called h , an update step called g , and three gates: an input i , a forget c , and an output o . LSTM computation at a time is t given as follows:

$$f_t = \text{sig}(x_t w_{xf} + h_{t-1} w_{hf} + \text{bias}_{hf} + \text{bias}_{xf}) \quad (1)$$

$$i_t = \text{sig}(x_t w_{xi} + h_{t-1} w_{hi} + \text{bias}_{xi} + \text{bias}_{hi}) \quad (2)$$

$$o_t = \text{sig}(x_t w_{xo} + h_{t-1} w_{ho} + \text{bias}_{xo} + \text{bias}_{ho}) \quad (3)$$

$$c_t = f_t \odot c_{t-1} + i_t \odot \text{ta}(x_t w_{xg} + h_{t-1} w_{hg} + \text{bias}_{xg} + \text{bias}_{hg}) \quad (4)$$

$$h_t = o_t \odot \tanh(c_{t-1}) \quad (5)$$

Here, sig is the sigmoid activation function, \tanh is the hyperbolic activation function, and \odot represents elementwise multiplication. The w_x 's and w_h 's are the input-hidden and hidden-hidden weights, respectively, and b_x 's and b_h 's are the corresponding biases. The LSTM cells are responsible for learning dependencies in sequences more effectively than traditional recurrent neural networks (RNNs) [11]. The gate within the cell controls the flow of information through the cell and determines which information is to be remembered and which is to be forgotten. LSTMs are successful at forecasting energy because of their memory structure, although conventional LSTMs need offline training.

4. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

Energy forecasting in residential buildings plays an essential role in helping a smart grid manage and conserve energy to ensure optimal use and avoid waste. However, accurate forecasting of power use can be difficult due to the impact of various unforeseeable events or the noise in the data, and the methods sometimes produce inaccurate predictions. An effective learning mechanism is necessary for precise load prediction. Electricity Load Prediction models are trained on historical data generated by smart meter sensors. This data may contain missing, redundant, and outlier values due to a variety of factors, such as meter sensor faults, fluctuating weather conditions, and unusual customer consumption patterns. To ensure the accuracy of the model, input raw datasets must be refined before training. In the present work, the model is trained to fill in any missing values and remove any outlier values. Then the data is passed to the proposed model for learning, as demonstrated in Fig. 3. This study utilized a numerical scale of power consumption data. The difference between minimum and maximum power values has a significant impact on the training speed and the convergence accuracy of the network. Normalization has been employed to enhance the computational speed and speed up the network training convergence.

Fig. 3 Flowchart of proposed power forecasting LSTM model

In this study, the LSTM model was proposed and compared with Bi-LSTM, a GRU, and an RNN. The following hyper-parameters were used to train the network. The loss function was the MSE, and the optimization was performed using the Adam optimizer which has been predominantly used in a regression problem. The optimizer is named “Adam” because it uses the first and second moments of the gradient estimates to change the learning rate individually per network weight. The name is derived from adaptive

moment estimation. Initially, the learning rate of 0.01 was applied to network optimization. The model's performance was quantified using the RMSE, MSE, and MAE. The experimental result demonstrates that the proposed LSTM model significantly reduces the error rate compared to other models.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, the dataset is thoroughly discussed, the proposed approach is assessed, experiments are conducted on datasets, and a comparison of state-of-the-art methods is provided. The model was trained over a Ryzen 5 5600H with Radeon GPU (Graphics Processing Unit) with 64-bit OS (Operating System) using the MATLAB 2021b framework.

A. Dataset

The performance of the deep learning model is evaluated using two benchmark datasets, the AEP dataset and the IHEPC dataset from the UCI repository [47,40]. The AEP dataset comprises 27 various parameters of weather information (wind speed, humidity, dew point, visibility, temperature, and pressure), light, and appliance energy consumption, as presented in Table II and the sample dataset is provided in Table V. The dataset is at 10 min resolution for about 4.5 months. A wireless sensor network was used to collect the data samples, both indoors and outdoors. The building has 9 indoor and 1 outdoor temperature sensor and 10 indoor moisture sensors of which 9 are indoors and 1 is outdoor. The indoor house temperature and humidity conditions were monitored with a ZigBee wireless sensor network. The outdoor pressure, visibility, temperature, humidity, and dew point from the nearest airport weather station (Chievres Airport, Belgium) were downloaded from a public data set from Reliable Prognosis and combined with the data from experiment sets using the date and time column.

TABLE II
DESCRIPTION AND UNITS OF AEP PARAMETERS DATASET

S.no	Parameters	Units
1	Date & Time	dd/mm/yyyy hh: mm: ss
2	Temperature of the kitchen (T1)	C
3	Humidity in the kitchen (RH1)	%
4	Temperature of the living room (T2)	C
5	Humidity of the living room (RH2)	%
6	Temperature of the laundry room (T3)	C
7	Humidity of the laundry room (RH3)	%
8	Temperature of the office room (T4)	C
9	Humidity of the office room (RH4)	%
10	Temperature of the bathroom (T5)	C
11	Humidity of the bathroom (RH5)	%
12	Outside temperature of building (T6)	C
13	Outside humidity of building (RH6)	%
14	Temperature of the ironing room (T7)	C
15	Humidity in the ironing room (RH7)	%
16	Temperature of the teenager's room (T8)	C
17	Humidity of the teenager room (RH8)	%
18	Temperature of the parent room (T9)	C
19	Humidity of the parent room (RH9)	%
20	Outside temperature collected from Chievres Weather Station (CWS) (Tout)	C
21	Outside pressure collected from CWS (Pout)	Mm Hg
22	Outside humidity from CWS (RHout)	%
23	Outside wind speed collected from CWS	m/s
24	Outside visibility from CWS	Km

25	Outside Tdewpoint from CWS	C
26	Total energy consumption by appliances	Wh
27	Total energy consumption by lights	Wh

TABLE III
 DESCRIPTION AND UNITS OF IHEPC PARAMETERS DATASET

S.no	Parameters	Units	Parameter remarks
1	Date	dd/mm/yyyy	Date in format days, months, and years
2	Time	hh: mm: ss	Time in format hours, minutes, and seconds
3	Voltage	V	The minute-averaged voltage
4	GI	Amp	The household global minute-averaged current intensity
5	Sub metering-1	w	It represents the kitchen, which is primarily equipped with a microwave, an oven, and a dishwasher
6	Sub metering-2	w	It represents the laundry room, which is primarily equipped with a washing machine, a tumble drier, a refrigerator, and a light
7	Sub metering-3	w	It represents the electric water heater and an air-conditioner
8	GRP	Kw	The household global minute-averaged reactive power
9	GAP	Kw	The household global minute-averaged active power

TABLE IV
 SAMPLE IHEPC DATASET

S. No	Date (dd/mm/yyyy)	Time (hh: mm: ss)	Voltage (V)	Global Intensity (Amp)	Sub metering 1 (w)	Sub metering 2 (w)	Sub metering 3 (w)	Global Reactive Power (Kw)	Global Active Power (Kw)
1	16-12-2006	17:24:00	234.84	18.4	0	1	17	0.418	4.216
2	16-12-2006	17:25:00	233.63	23	0	1	16	0.436	5.36
3	16-12-2006	17:26:00	233.29	23	0	2	17	0.498	5.374
4	16-12-2006	17:27:00	233.74	23	0	1	17	0.502	5.388
5	16-12-2006	17:28:00	235.68	15.8	0	1	17	0.528	3.666
6	16-12-2006	17:29:00	235.02	15	0	2	17	0.522	3.52
7	16-12-2006	17:30:00	235.09	15.8	0	1	17	0.52	3.702
8	16-12-2006	17:31:00	235.22	15.8	0	1	17	0.52	3.7
9	16-12-2006	17:32:00	233.99	15.8	0	1	17	0.51	3.668
10	16-12-2006	17:24:00	234.84	18.4	0	1	17	0.418	4.216

TABLE V
 SAMPLE AEP DATASET

S. No	Date & Time (dd/mm/yyyy) (hh: mm: ss)	TI (C)	RHI (%)	T2 (C)	RH2 (%)	T3 (C)	RH3 (%)	T4 (C)	RH4 (%)	T5 (C)	RH5 (%)	T6 (C)	RH6 (%)	T7 (C)	RH7 (%)	T8 (C)	RH8 (%)	T9 (C)	RH9 (%)	Tout (C)	Pout (Mm Hg)	Rhout (%)
1	11-01-2016 17:00	19.89	47.60	19.20	44.79	19.79	44.73	19.00	45.57	17.17	55.20	7.03	84.26	17.20	41.62	18.2	48.96	17.03	45.53	6.60	733.5	92
2	11-01-2016 17:10	19.89	46.69	19.20	44.72	19.79	44.79	19.00	45.99	17.17	55.20	6.83	84.06	17.20	41.56	18.2	48.86	17.03	45.56	6.48	733.6	92
3	11-01-2016 17:20	19.89	46.30	19.20	44.63	19.79	44.93	18.93	45.89	17.17	55.09	6.56	83.16	17.20	41.43	18.2	48.73	17	45.5	6.37	733.7	92
4	11-01-2016 17:30	19.89	46.07	19.20	44.59	19.79	45.00	18.89	45.72	17.17	55.09	6.43	83.42	17.13	41.29	18.1	48.59	17	45.4	6.25	733.8	92
5	11-01-2016 17:40	19.89	46.33	19.20	44.53	19.79	45.00	18.89	45.53	17.20	55.09	6.37	84.89	17.20	41.23	18.1	48.59	17	45.4	6.13	733.9	92
6	11-01-2016 17:50	19.89	46.03	19.20	44.50	19.79	44.93	18.89	45.73	17.13	55.03	6.30	85.77	17.13	41.26	18.1	48.59	17	45.29	6.02	734.0	92
7	11-01-2016 18:00	19.89	45.77	19.20	44.50	19.79	44.90	18.89	45.79	17.10	54.97	6.26	86.09	17.13	41.26	18.1	48.59	17	45.29	5.90	734.1	92
8	11-01-2016 18:10	19.86	45.56	19.20	44.50	19.73	44.90	18.89	45.86	17.10	54.90	6.19	86.42	17.10	41.25	18.1	48.59	17	45.29	5.92	734.2	91.8
9	11-01-2016 18:20	19.79	45.60	19.20	44.43	19.73	44.79	18.89	45.79	17.17	55.00	6.12	87.23	17.17	41.46	18.1	48.59	17	45.29	5.93	734.2	91.6
10	11-01-2016 17:00	19.89	47.60	19.23	44.40	19.79	44.86	18.89	46.10	17.10	55.00	6.19	87.63	17.20	41.54	18.1	48.59	17	45.29	6.60	733.5	92

In 2006 and 2010, the IHEPC dataset for a residential house located in France was recorded for a resolution of one minute. The data includes 9 parameters which are; date, time, voltage, sub metering-1 (kitchen), sub

metering-2 (laundry room), sub metering-3 (electric water heater and air conditioner), global intensity (GI), global-reactive-power (GRP) and global-active-power (GAP) as shown in Table III and sample dataset is provided in Table IV.

B. Experimentation results using IHEPC, AEP Dataset, and comparison with other models

In this study, an LSTM model is established. The general indicators used for evaluating the performance of a time-series data forecasting model include MAE, MSE, and RMSE. Let n be the number of test data, x_{pred} be the value predicted by the proposed algorithm, and x_{act} be the actual value in the quantitative.

MAE measures the absolute value of the difference between the predicted value and the actual value, as shown in Equation (6). A lower score denotes greater precision.

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{1}^n |x_{\text{pred}} - x_{\text{act}}| \quad (6)$$

RMSE, defined as in Equation (7), measures the average difference between predicted and actual values; it is a measure of the deviation between predicted and actual values. Better performance is indicated by RMSE that is nearer to 0. RMSE is sensitive to outliers, which makes it more susceptible to considerable variation, as compared to MAE. Since the error is squared, a larger error leads to weight being reflected to a greater extent.

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{1}^n (x_{\text{pred}} - x_{\text{act}})^2} \quad (7)$$

MSE calculates the average of the squared differences between the predicted values and the actual values of a variable of interest. It measures the average squared deviation between the predicted and actual values, giving higher weight to larger deviations. A lower MSE value indicates a better fit of the model to the data, as it means the predicted values are closer to the actual values on average. It is calculated using Equation (8).

$$\text{MSE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{1}^n (x_{\text{pred}} - x_{\text{act}})^2 \quad (8)$$

By considering these evaluation metrics, the deep learning model gains insights into the accuracy and quality of the predictions made by regression models and makes informed decisions when comparing or selecting models.

C. Experimentation results using IHEPC, AEP Dataset, and comparison with other models

This section compared the performance of the model proposed to those of existing models for predicting short-term loads using IHEPC data sets and AEP data sets. For the IHEPC dataset, the proposed LSTM model achieves 0.18, 0.03, and 0.12 RMSE, MSE, and MAE, respectively. Fig. 4 (a) demonstrates that the LSTM closely predicts the energy consumption better than the other deep learning methods. The comparison

of error metrics is also shown in Table VI. The LSTM network also predicts the native characteristics of the power consumption. The proposed model also observes that it organizes and models the irregular inclinations of power consumption more effectively. Also, the study confirms that the complex pattern generated by the time series model of power consumption is predicted appropriately, and shows that the proposed method moderates the error at each interval compared to Bi-LSTM, GRU, and RNN. The prediction series for the original input data to Bi-LSTM, GRU, and RNN are given in Fig. 4 (b), Fig. 4 (c), and Fig. 4 (d), respectively.

Fig. 4 Graph obtained for prediction of power consumption. Power is expressed in kW. (a) represents the prediction results for LSTM. The suggested LSTM provides a pattern that is very close to the power consumed. Graphs (b), (c), and (d) illustrate the results for Bi-LSTM, GRU, and RNN respectively for the IHEPC dataset

TABLE VI
 COMPARISON OF ERROR METRICS FOR VARIOUS DEEP LEARNING TECHNIQUES PROPOSED FOR THE IHEPC DATASET

Method	RMSE	MSE	MAE
LSTM	0.18	0.03	0.12
GRU	0.21	0.04	0.10
Bi-LSTM	0.24	0.06	0.02
RNN	0.53	0.28	0.14

TABLE VII
 COMPARISON OF ERROR METRICS FOR VARIOUS DEEP LEARNING TECHNIQUES PROPOSED FOR THE AEP DATASET

Method	RMSE	MSE	MAE
LSTM	0.05	0.02	0.02
GRU	0.26	0.06	0.25
Bi-LSTM	0.35	0.12	0.33
RNN	0.15	0.03	0.05

TABLE VIII

DETAILED PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF COMPETITIVE STATE-OF-THE-ART TECHNIQUES WITH THE PROPOSED METHOD OVER IHEPC DATASET

Methods	RMSE	MSE	MAE
CNN-2D-RP [41]	0.79	-	0.59
CNN-LSTM [42]	0.59	0.35	0.33
CNN-LSTM-AE [43]	0.47	0.19	0.31
CNN-MLBDLSTM [44]	0.56	0.31	0.34
SE-AE [45]	-	0.38	0.39
FCRBM [46]	0.66	-	-
CNN-GRU [29]	0.47	0.22	0.33
DCNN-MB-GRU [48]	0.42	0.18	0.29
Proposed LSTM	0.18	0.03	0.12

TABLE IX

A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS OF COMPETITIVE STATE-OF-THE-ART TECHNIQUES USING THE PROPOSED METHODOLOGY OVER AN AEP DATASET

Methods	RMSE	MSE	MAE
XGBoost [49]	0.59	-	0.26
GBM [42]	0.35	-	0.66
AIS-RNN [43]	0.59	-	-
CNN-GRU [29]	0.31	0.09	0.24
DCNN-MB-GRU [48]	0.29	0.10	0.23
Proposed LSTM	0.15	0.02	0.05

Additionally, the proposed model's performance is assessed using the AEP dataset for a short-term horizon. The proposed model achieved a RMSE of 0.15, a MSE of 0.02 and a MAE of 0.05 for the AEP dataset. Table. VI and table VII illustrates the comparison of proposed deep learning model for IHEPC and AEP dataset. It clearly shows that LSTM outperforms the other techniques.

D. Comparative analysis of the proposed method

The model's performance over the IHEPC dataset is also compared to other base-line methods. In [41], deep learning was used for residential load prediction resulting in an RMSE of 0.79 and an MAE of 0.59. In [42], the authors employed a CNN-LSTM hybrid network for short-term residential load forecasting resulting in RMSE of 0.59, MSE of 0.35, and MAE of 0.33 respectively. In [45], the authors achieved an MSE of 0.38 and an MAE of 0.39. In [46], they achieved a RMSE of 0.66. In another strategy described in [29], they achieved RMSE at 0.47, MSE at 0.22, and MAE at 0.33. The findings are compared with these models and confirmed that the proposed method outperforms the state-of-art techniques. The blank area in Table.8 represents that the mentioned techniques have not used the corresponding metrics for evaluation such as RMSE, MAE, etc., Table VIII summarises the performance of the existing and proposed methods for IHEPC dataset that verify the effectiveness of the proposed method.

Similarly, the effectiveness of the proposed model over the AEP dataset is also compared with other baseline models, as shown in Table IX. For instance, the results are compared with [44,49–51]. For further details,

Ref. [49] achieved 0.59 RMSE and 0.26 MSE, Ref. [50] achieved 0.35 RMSE and 0.66 MSE, and [51] achieved 0.59 RMSE. In [29], authors achieved 0.31, 0.09, and 0.24 scores for RMSE, MSE, and MAE, respectively. Compared to these models, the proposed LSTM model performed better in reducing the RMSE and MAE error rates.

6. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

Accurate load prediction is extremely important for energy saving and has significant economic impacts. According to [29], reducing the error rate by 1% in the load prediction model can save \$1.6M per year and save 10,000 MW of electricity. The rapid expansion of urbanization has made it increasingly important to forecast energy consumption efficiency. Commercial and residential buildings account for around 40% of energy consumption. These predictive models can help to bridge the gap between the supply and demand of electrical energy. In addition, this forecast is of global importance as it guides government planners and policy-makers. Therefore, new auto-mated models are necessary to enhance the accuracy of energy consumption predictions. This paper applies a deep learning technique for forecasting residential electricity consumption behavior. As a result, the proposed method provides minimal error. It should be noted that it overrides all other previous works related to deep learning-based forecasting. In the future, real-time data will be collected through the smart meter and a forecasting model will be designed. Also, a study will apply to propose a novel deep learning approach for improving electricity consumption forecasting based on hybrid LSTM algorithms for medium- to long-term electricity consumption forecasting. Along with this, additional evaluation metrics will also be applied to test the accuracy.

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